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[The Impact of Entrepreneurial Education on Entrepreneurial Career Adaptability with Mediating Role of Self Efficacy]

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the relationship between entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurial career adaptability, likewise the way it makes a significant contribution to entrepreneurial success. The study intends to provide a route way for individuals to benefit themselves with a positive effect on entrepreneurial self-efficacy. The data was obtained from the final year graduate students of mandatory entrepreneurship courses to analyze the link between entrepreneurial education, intentions, and success, while using the Likert scale as a tool. This study used cluster random sampling, a total of 400 university students aged 22 to 24 years (Mean age = 23) were selected as respondents. The strongest linear relationship was found between Entrepreneurial Self-efficacy and Entrepreneurial Intention ($r = .885, p = .001$). Besides Entrepreneurial Education the main predictor of career intention ($\beta = .518, p = .005$), and self-esteem ($\beta = .463, p = .005$) also contributed significantly to Entrepreneurial Intention. Entrepreneurial Self-efficacy was found to significantly mediate the influences of and relationship between Entrepreneurial Intention and Entrepreneurial Education. Hence, it can be suggested by the results that Self-efficacy of undergraduate students is substantially associated with Entrepreneurial Intention leading to career adaptability, which plays an important role in efficiency and employability of graduates. It accounts for greater attention to be put on using entrepreneurial education as a medium for being a successful entrepreneur.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial education, Entrepreneurial Career Adaptability, Self-Efficacy

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the last few years, the entrepreneurial mindset has been considered as the result of failure and success among entrepreneurs (Beluosova et al., 2020). Generally, policymakers and academics have accepted that the main power in running economic development is “entrepreneurship”. Consequently, education facilities and initiatives have come out and are designed to support entrepreneurial development (Stamboulis & Barlas, 2014). Various advances have been made by policy implementation all around the country to upgrade entrepreneurial activity, particularly among graduates. The study aims to ensemble a couple of areas primarily. Firstly, education reforms in universities increase their positive impact on human capital by polishing the employment skills of graduates. Secondly, entrepreneurial education not only acts as a catalyst for entrepreneurial activity for university graduates but also improves opportunities for them in job marketing (Sin & Neave, 2016).

The knowledge of entrepreneurial education helps students in business management and development by arousing their concern regarding the company’s growth. Economic development and entrepreneurial activity are connected repeatedly; it is accepted by researchers that the rise of small organizations and new ventures impacts social results as well as economic development, both at the local and national level (Pedrini et.al., 2017). Along with possessing specialized knowledge and abilities, university graduates should also be adaptable, have a good outlook on work, be self-

motivated, and be eager to pick up new information and skills. (Cronin-Golomb, L. & Bauer, 2023). Therefore, it is crucial to pinpoint the variables that affect job adaptability so that students are familiar with suitable intervention strategies before they graduate. If specific organizations function and operate properly, entrepreneurship in specific cases becomes more advantageous for development and growth. Both public and private organizations need to coordinate to build up an encouraging atmosphere for those who want to be “entrepreneurs”. It has been revealed that entrepreneurial self-efficacy (ESE) has a positive link with the intentions of a business startup. These have led entrepreneurship scholars to evaluate relative ESE significance (for sustainable antecedent factors of EI such as age or gender, risk propensity, and education) for the creation of actions and entrepreneurial career adaptability.

It is vital to understand ESE how it is established and how it can be anticipated. Entrepreneurship can be viewed as an important driver in several transitioning and developing economies toward economic growth. Students are considered to be an integral constituent of creative activities at universities. Thus, it is critically important for students at the university level to develop an entrepreneurial spirit and potential to gain knowledge on entrepreneurship and for planning future business.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Entrepreneurship has become a popular career choice among individuals seeking autonomy, financial independence, and job satisfaction. Entrepreneurship education plays a vital and significant role in students’ development of ESE. Entrepreneurial education explains how to improve entrepreneurial pursuits’ knowledge, skills, attitudes, and personal roles (Hussain & Norashidah, 2015).

While several studies have investigated the impact of entrepreneurial education on various aspects of entrepreneurial career development, there is limited research on its influence on entrepreneurial career adaptability. Moreover, the mediating role of self-efficacy in this relationship has not been explored comprehensively. The present study has focused that there is a need to work on entrepreneurial education which may help students to take the initiative for self-employment. Students may learn with the help of EE to enhance their abilities for business. This research analyses the impact of EE on EI & and will prove that SE influences EI development. So, this study inspects the relationship between students’ EE and entrepreneurial mindset along with their understanding of the intermediate role of self-awareness.

1.2 Research Questions

1. What could be the possible effects of EE on entrepreneurial career adaptability and entrepreneurial self-efficiency?
2. How does entrepreneurial self-efficacy affect entrepreneurial career adaptability?
3. How does entrepreneurial self-efficacy act as a mediator between entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurial career adaptability?

1.3 Research Objectives

1. To inspect the significant positive effect of entrepreneurial self-efficacy on entrepreneurial adaptability.

2. To inspect the mediation of entrepreneurial self-efficacy between entrepreneurial education and adaptability.
3. To find out the significant positive effect of EE on entrepreneurial career adaptability and entrepreneurial self-efficacy.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The need for and the importance of this study is evident in the works that have already been done in this field. These contributions show that there is a dire need for study in this particular field. Potential entrepreneurs can learn through the modeling of effective business operations and behavior (Boldureanu et al., 2020). As stated entrepreneurship studies in higher education benefit students' basic competence and skills in entrepreneurship and reinforce students' EI. Practically, research shows that entrepreneurship education could help influence the development of EI.

Self-efficacy is faith in one's ability to utilize needed competencies, resources, knowledge, and skills to achieve goals (Gielnik et al., 2020). High levels of self-efficacy are associated with high levels of self-perceived competence and self-image. (Adigun, 2020). Through the demonstration of high self-efficacy, they are driven to create challenging career objectives and take appropriate action. Individuals with a high level of self-efficacy are bound to engage in activities connected to their job growth, and as a result, they are more likely to develop personalities and flexibility that are appropriate for careers. When faced with obstacles, they are self-assured and easily modify their ways. (Atac et al., 2018). Self-efficacy, or a person's opinion of their value, would therefore improve their capacity to deal with changes in the workplace. A key predictor of occupational flexibility, according to previous research by Hui et al. (2018), Ismail (2017), and Atac et al. (2018) is self-efficacy. In other words, increasing self-efficacy would boost employability while also increasing career versatility. Thus, one of the goals of the current study is to examine the connection between undergraduate students' self-efficacy and entrepreneurial career intention.

ESE is a substantial motivating factor in the entrepreneurship process though since people accept the terms of the ambiguity that surrounds the business circumstances, which require proper effort, planning, and persistence (Newman et al., 2019). Entrepreneurship education plays a vital role in the growth of students' EI and ESE.

2.1 Entrepreneurial Education and Entrepreneurial Intention

According to Gibcus et al., (2012), *"The essential skills of students in entrepreneurship by improving the 'EI' of graduates strengthen entrepreneurship curriculum in higher education"*. Empirically, studies show that education in entrepreneurship may influence EI growth (Pedrini et al., 2017) at the Catholic Institute of Technology and Business (In Accra) used the *"E4impact MBA"* curriculum as a case study and found that entrepreneurship preparation greatly raises the EI of students. Doan and Phan (2020) performed the study on 688 students from business and technical universities in Vietnam's northern region. The findings demonstrated a significant influence of EE on the entrepreneurial intention in the North of Vietnam. EE likewise usefully affected self-

efficacy and entrepreneurship fervor simultaneously. Time along with teamwork continued to play a statistically significant moderate influence an association between student entrepreneurial intention and entrepreneurial education. For more than 20 years, researchers have employed the Theory of planned behavior to inspect how entrepreneurial education (EE) affects entrepreneurial intention (EI). However, a thorough literature assessment indicates that both the conceptual framework and research techniques are lacking. Given the literature, the first hypothesis that assists in this study is:

Hypothesis 1: Entrepreneurial Education should have an important progressive effect on Entrepreneurial Career Adaptability or Entrepreneurial Intention.

2.2 Entrepreneurial Education and Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy

R. A. Baron (2004) defines self-efficacy even as “*trust in the capability of ace to assemble and execute the tools, abilities, and competencies required to reach the standard of achievement*”. However, there are different opinions on how self-efficacy is created (Rauch & Hulsink, 2015) also found that entrepreneurship schooling in entrepreneurship improves assumed regulation over students’ behaviors. Education in the arena of entrepreneurship will play a vital role in the ESE student’s improvement. The study by Sun et al., (2017) suggested a conceptual framework that connected all of the antecedent factors to the expanded four elements of entrepreneurship education. (How, Why, Who, and What). A structural equation modeling analysis using the empirical data from 200 engineering students from three institutions in Hong Kong was used to evaluate the model which revealed that the four components of EE do influence the social norm, attitude, EI, and self-efficacy, respectively.

According to Hussain and Norashidah (2015), entrepreneurial education is a type of learning that focuses on developing knowledge, abilities, attitudes, and personal character associated with entrepreneurship. Like other subjects, entrepreneurship may be studied and promoted via published advancements in understanding, abilities, mindsets, and character that enhance students' success in entrepreneurship-related activities. Students can improve their critical thinking skills related to entrepreneurship by transitioning from a teacher-centered to a learner-centered educational approach (Commarmond, 2017). After completing entrepreneurship courses, students are also able to identify the key teaching methodology, which consists of giving a business practice, visiting a firm, and interviewing a successful entrepreneur. To improve their entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial abilities, this teaching method—which uses contextual learning and offers a practical experience rather than a theory—is seen to be the most important (Potishuk and Kratzer, 2017). These students will develop an even stronger entrepreneurial attitude if the content and methods used to teach practical entrepreneurship courses are carefully considered. Bringing up these theories, several earlier studies have suggested links between self-efficacy perception, entrepreneurial mentality, and entrepreneurship education.

Hypothesis 2: Entrepreneurial Education should have a significant beneficial impact on ESE.

2.3 Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy and Entrepreneurial Intention

ESE is considered an essential feature of the entrepreneurial practice because folks embrace the uncertain terms concerning the market scenario that demands commitment, patience, and preparation (Newman et al., 2019). Bergey et al., (2019) state the rate of high self-efficacy is related to taking strategic risks. Individuals with strong self-efficacy appear to show greater inherent preferences in company practices and events. According to Sussman, Gifford, (2019). people would show a larger preference for a certain action and then develop the desire to carry it out if they think doing so will lead to a favorable outcome. Self-efficacy has been shown to influence individuals' objective setting to conduct a conviction to achieve this goal. For the entrepreneurs, there is a strong association between their intellect of self-worth and entrepreneurial intention (Ko & Kim, 2020). Accordingly, it is claimed in the study of Liu et al., (2019) that entrepreneurs will have a more decisive entrepreneurial attitude if they think they can carry out and accomplish an entrepreneurial assignment.

According to Pihie and Bagheri (2013), self-efficacy has a significant impact on people's decision to take action despite the availability of alternatives, the amount of work required to complete the action, their tenacity in the face of setbacks, and their chances for action. In a similar vein, Wardana (2020) contended that self-efficacy is the primary element influencing behavior through goal-setting, process, result expectations, and situational obstacles. Researchers have been studying the idea of entrepreneurial self-efficacy in the field of entrepreneurship because of its underlying influence on people's behavior.

Hypothesis 3: ESE should exhibit considerable positive influence upon EI.

2.4 ESE Mediating Role Between EI and ESE

The question of how EE affects university students' EI in the Visegrád nations was examined in the research by Nowinski et al., published in 2019. According to the findings, there are some disparities between the four countries when it comes to how education and entrepreneurial self-efficacy (ESE) affect entrepreneurial goals. Poland, the only nation out of the four to offer entrepreneurship instruction at the high school level, saw a direct, positive, and considerable influence from it. Additionally, it was discovered that EE indirectly influenced EI. The study demonstrates that, even though these effects vary amongst the analyzed nations, ESEs related to seeking, planning, and marshaling tasks mitigate the influence of entrepreneurial education on intentions. It is evident from the prior discussion that education in entrepreneurship plays a serious part in the betterment and growth of the IE and ESE of the students. Likewise, ESE may affect EI development. Therefore, conceptually ESE should include pathways for education in entrepreneurship to impact EI.

Hypothesis 4: ESE mediates the relationship between EI and EE.

2.5 Theoretical Framework

Ajzen (2020) introduced the theory of planned behavior. According to this theory, a person's purpose for a particular conduct influences how likely that behavior is to occur. The way a the person feels about himself and stereotypes his intentions. The

likelihood that conduct would result in the expected results, the acceptability, resulting in light of the social norms of a reference group, and the attractiveness of those results all contribute to the establishment of an attitude. Furthermore, according to the Theory of Planned Behavior, an individual's attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control all influence their entrepreneurial purpose.

Perception of behavioral control moderates the impact of attitude toward the behavior and subjective norm on intention. Generally speaking, a person's desire to carry out the activity in issue should be stronger the more positive their attitude and subjective norm are, as well as the higher their perceived control. Ultimately, people are expected to act on their intentions when presented with the chance, provided they have a sufficient level of real control over their actions. Therefore, it is considered that conduct has an immediate cause, which is intention. If perceived behavioral control is accurate, it can operate as a stand-in for real behavioral control and help forecast the behavior under consideration.

We also use the career construction theory in an educational environment in the current study (Savickas, 2013). According to the notion, professional success is influenced by an individual's adaptability within an organization, including how they prepare for and handle changes in their career as well as transitions. Additionally, according to the career-building theory, five behaviors—orientation, exploration, establishment, management, and disengagement—are what promote adaptability to these shifts. An ongoing process of adaptation is formed by all these beneficial processes. For instance, when new graduates start working in new roles and explore the responsibilities and routines of such employment, they go through a development phase. Then, they establish themselves in their positions, stay in them for a while, and then gradually leave them when other prospects for employment present themselves (Akkermans et al., 2018).

While entrepreneurial education offered by universities is the basis of entrepreneurial knowledge and skills to improve an individual's quality of entrepreneurship and a crucial factor in entrepreneurial success, it has not gotten enough responsiveness in the previously mentioned cognitive factors. To investigate the impacts of EE and SE on college students' EI, this article employed the Career Construction Theory and Theory of Planned Behavior, demonstrated by the model given below:

Conceptual Model Formulation of Hypothesis

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

For this quantitative analysis researcher will utilize a 5-point Likert scale as a tool for rating the student performance. It will help to identify the benefits of entrepreneurial education entrepreneurial career adaptability in academic domains and how knowledge of entrepreneurship improves the self-efficiency and make them self-employed. The following conceptual model formulated for the study will enable the researcher to explore the need and significance of EE, EI, & and SE in present times.

3.2 Sample of the Study

A group of 400 university students will be chosen as a sample for this study. The main objective of the current study is to investigate the relationship between entrepreneurial career adaptability and entrepreneurial education which might help students to create employment opportunities for themselves. It is anticipated that entrepreneurship courses will allow them to build their employment. So, this study will select the final-year university students enrolled in mandatory entrepreneurship courses as a primary source for data collection.

3.3 Data Collection Tool

According to the definition of self-efficacy perception, it is the conviction that one is capable of engaging in entrepreneurial activity based on an assessment of their management, functional, and technical skills. Explanatory factor analysis was used to analyze the scale, and 22 items with more than 0.40-factor loadings were used to evaluate ESE perception. Six important dimensions of ESE perception were highlighted by the measure. The following are the dimensions: establishing investor relationships

(skills related to obtaining funds to capitalize the start-up company), creating an innovative environment (skills related to the capacity to inspire others), handling unforeseen challenges (skills to employ and develop human resources), and identifying the main aim (creating mission and vision and communicating effectively to attract key staff and investors). Taking into account the findings of explanatory factor analysis and its widespread usage in other studies, this scale was utilized in our investigation to quantify ESE.

3.1 Data Analysis Tool

The four items "I will probably own my own business one day," "Likely, I will personally own a small business in the relatively near future," "Being my boss is an important goal of mine," and "I often think of having my own business" were used to assess the respondents' entrepreneurial intentions. On a five-point Likert scale, responses to these questions were given (1=strongly disagree; 5=strongly agree). The gender, age, and family income level of participants were also requested because these demographic factors may be significant in entrepreneurship. This information was then inspected principally by correlation, linear multiple regression, and concise statistics. Key theories will be checked using multiple linear regression analysis. The data analysis will be facilitated with SPSS version 22.0.

3. RESULTS

4.1 Data Analysis

An analysis of the mediating role of Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy between Entrepreneurial Education and Entrepreneurial Intention/Career Adaptability is the aim of this research study. The information gathered from the targeted population through the survey questionnaire has been investigated and enlisted as follows:

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4.1.1 Demographics

In the study, three demographics were included. Male and Female final year students of Business Administration belonging to the age group 22-24 years (91.7%) were the targeted audience. The percentages of male and female respondents were: 74% were male (n = 400) and 26% were female (n=400). The data showed that the frequencies of monthly income of the family are as follows: 15.7% had less than Rs. 50,000, 63.5 % had family income between Rs. 50,000 to Rs. 100,000, and 20.7% had above Rs. 100,000. Their summary is given below:

Table 1: Age

Variable	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Below 22 years	33	8.25	15.8	95.2
22 to 24 years	367	4.8	4.8	100.0
Total	400	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	296	74.0	74.0	96.7
Female	104	26.0	26.0	100.0

Table 3: Family Income

Variable	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
Less than Rs. 50,000	63	15.7	15.7	15.7
Rs. 50,000 - 100,000	254	63.5	63.5	56.5
More than Rs. 100,000	83	20.7	20.7	76.1
Total	400	100.0	100.0	

4.1.1 Reliability Analysis

The Cronbach's alpha analysis is used to find out the internal reliability among the variables. It ranges between 0 and 1, according to (Gliem and Gilem, 2003). The rule of thumb indicated by (George and Mallery, 2019) for the interpretation of acceptability of Cronbach's alpha is above 0.80. The acceptable values lie between the range of 0.71-0.9; below this value, the internal consistency of the common range is low. The table shows that Cronbach's alphas of all scales are high for the current samples when compared with the threshold values. Therefore, the present scale Cronbach's alpha of emotional exhaustion ($\alpha = .885$), indicates good internal reliability. Thus, the reliability analysis of the present research proposes the internal consistency of the questionnaire. The reliability calculations are given below:

Table 4: Reliability of the scales

Variable	Cronbach Alpha
Entrepreneurial Education	.834
Entrepreneurial Intention/Career Adaptability	.851

Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy .885

4.1.2 Correlation Analysis

To recognize levels of importance between factors correlation analysis is done. Pearson's coefficient of correlation discovered the elevated levels of considerable positive correlations for all proportions of Entrepreneurial Education with Entrepreneurial Intention/Career Adaptability. Total scores of the relationship of these dimensions were calculated as suggested by Overbeek, Scholte, de Kemp, & Engels (2007), and as given in the following table .57 to .88 the suggested convergent validity of the questionnaire. Correlation has been utilized to investigate the linear relationship between the variables. The potency of correlation is calculated by complete assessment of correlation coefficient which may fall between -1 and +1. The correlation values disclose significant positive correlation between workload, workplace incivility and turnover intention. Correlation $r = 0$ indicates that there is no linear relationship between the variables. The course of the relationship is shown by the indication of coefficient.

Table 5: Correlations

Variables	1	2	3	4
1. EE	1			
2. ESE	.365**	1		
3. EI	.476**	.646**	1	

N=400, ** $p < 0.01$.

4.1.3 Mediation Analysis

The association among dependent and related factors that is put away in an information document is found throughout mediation analysis. The reason of the change in the value of an interdependent variable can affect the dependent data is also explained through it. The primary prerequisite of mediation analysis is to perceive the idea of relationship among related factors.

Table 6: Mediation effect of emotional exhaustion between Entrepreneurial Education, Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy, and Entrepreneurial Intention

	B	SE	Tp	
Entrepreneurial Education \longrightarrow Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy	.463	.077	6.026	.000
Entrepreneurial Education \longrightarrow Entrepreneurial Intention	.518	.067	7.784	.000
Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy \longrightarrow Entrepreneurial Intention	.666	.066	10.131	.000
Entrepreneurial Education \longrightarrow Entrepreneurial Intention	.118	.072	1.651	.001
Self-Efficacy \longrightarrow Entrepreneurial Intention				
Bootstrap result for indirect effect	Indirect Effect	LL 95% CI	UL 95% CI	
		.248	.453	
				.345

Results demonstrate that with the increase in EE, EI and Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy are also increased which supports our first and second hypothesis i.e.

H1: EE has an important progressive effect on EI.

H2: EE has a significant beneficial impact on Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy.

The mediation of Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy is shown to be partial mediation as the beta value lessened in terms of both workload and workplace incivility. Mediation estimates of Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy is 0.561, which indicates the positive relation between both variables, p values less than 0.05 shows the significance of the relationship. The acceptance of our fourth hypothesis is observed.

H3: Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy should exhibit considerable positive influence upon Entrepreneurial Intention.

The EI and EE are positively linked with Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy, and the estimated value shows low levels of Entrepreneurial Education & Entrepreneurial Intention can reduce Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy of students. P value indicates the significance of relationship and acceptance of fourth hypothesis:

H4: Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy mediates the relationship between EI and EE

Mediation estimates of Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy in the relationship between EI and EE are

0.25 and 0.118 respectively, which shows the immediate relationship but is not critical thus, demonstrating our hypotheses.

4.1.4 Accepted/Rejected Hypothesis:

Table: Summary of Hypothesis Rejection/ Acceptance

Hypothesis	Statements	Results
H1	Entrepreneurial Education has a significant progressive effect on Entrepreneurial Intention.	Supported
H2	Entrepreneurial Education has a significant beneficial impact on Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy.	Supported
H3	Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy should exhibit considerable	Supported

4. DISCUSSION

This study builds an impact creating model to assess students' EI using entrepreneurial education as independent variables and self-efficacy as a mediator. In terms of learning and self-efficacy, it strengthened and added to the Theory of Planned Behavior. Results offer empirical proof for preexisting hypotheses and will be a useful resource for further research.

Entrepreneurial self-efficacy has a significant and positive effect on EI, and it further mediates the relationships between entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurial intention. The research highlights that EE has a significant and positive effect on students' EI but not on their attitude towards entrepreneurship. These outcomes support the development of entrepreneurship theories and serve as a significant source of inspiration for Pakistani students' entrepreneurial accomplishments with delivery of entrepreneurship education in universities and other associated facilities to provide training.

In terms of the socio-psychological perspective of entrepreneurship, this study's findings are helpful. The idea of self-efficacy merits additional consideration in entrepreneurship research since an existence of a favorable association between entrepreneurial intention and ESE. The study also assesses the findings in a society with a high level of collectivism and uncertainty avoidance. Despite the fact that the cultural traits do not encourage entrepreneurship, the moderate to strong correlations between ESE qualities and EI suggest that the self-efficacy theory might become useful in identifying the variables that influence EI. The qualities that have a shaky relationship with EI show that there are other significant elements besides ESE.

The state of entrepreneurial education in Pakistan at the moment is another matter that needs to be looked into. The importance of entrepreneurship education in

encouraging young people to become entrepreneurs is growing. However, the majority of entrepreneurship courses place a heavy emphasis on technical skills while ignoring concerns like an entrepreneurial mentality, cultural restrictions on entrepreneurship, and the unique traits that people develop as a result of their interactions with society. Thus, entrepreneurship courses have to place greater emphasis on socio-psychological and cognitive ideas like self-efficacy. Students can identify their entrepreneurial potential and evaluate an influence of factors such as social & cultural at the same time in this way. Therefore, by teaching these kids effectively and assisting them in overcoming their ineptitude, their potential may be enhanced.

5.1 Limitations

The study's shortcomings must be acknowledged, despite the fact that the research's findings contain many valuable conclusions. First off, rather than actual business owners, the study's participants are students. A sample of students may be used to get crucial data on ESE and the entrepreneurial ambition of young people in Pakistan. It is crucial to back up the study's conclusions with further investigation through these concepts using a sample of entrepreneurs from the actual world. Causative conclusions are inappropriate given the cross-sectional nature of the data employed in this study. Therefore, the only logical conclusion is that entrepreneurial intent positively correlates with ESE characteristics. Future studies should use a longitudinal approach to infer causal relationships between the aforementioned factors. Additionally, there was no question in this survey that aimed to find out what respondents did to fulfil their entrepreneurial intentions. The relationship between ESE and EI will be made clearer by questions concerning real self-employment preparedness. Therefore, future studies should evaluate genuine entrepreneurial training.

5. CONCLUSION

Considering Pakistan's rising unemployment rates and its related social and economic crisis, stakeholders are adopting the education concept in entrepreneurship as a significant medium for defining the human resources for high employment. Hence, this study investigated whether entrepreneurial education would affect entrepreneurial career adaptability while taking into account ESE's mediating role. The research discovered that EE has a constructive impact on EI, suggesting that if students are introduced to entrepreneurial education to fit them with entrepreneurship, awareness, and opportunities identification skills, they should establish a greater purpose of business participation. Furthermore, the consequence of the present study revealed that ESE is indeed an integral aspect of transforming the EE into EI, and thus accounts for greater attention to be put on utilizing entrepreneurial education as a medium to instill trust in students to become effective and successful professionals.

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